

Livelihood and Living Conditions of Traditional Cane and Bamboo Artisans in Aizawl and Kolasib Districts, Mizoram

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Abstract

India has several artisan communities dispersed across its states and regions. The declining production shows a decrease of artisans in every community. Most of the handicraft artisans belong to socially and economically weaker sections of the Indian society. The Mizos have many traditional handicraft products made from cane and bamboo. This skill had been passed on from one generation to the other until the machine-made products replaced them. However, there still are a few traditional handicraft items which machine-made items cannot replace and are highly socially valued. In this context, the present paper probes into the differential patterns of livelihood assets and living conditions of tribal bamboo and cane artisans in Mizoram between the rural and urban areas. Further, it explores the relationship between the livelihood assets and living conditions of them. Livelihood and living conditions of tribal artisans in rural areas and urban areas differ significantly. The urban artisans have comparatively better chances and better opportunities in all walks of life, and have better livelihood assets and enjoy better living conditions. However, urban artisans produce less and spend less time on work but their income and expenditure are very much higher than those of the hard-working rural artisans. In light of these findings, a few suggestions for policy making and social work practice towards livelihood promotion of tribal artisans in the state are put forth.

Key Words: Livelihood, living conditions, handicrafts, artisans

Introduction

In India, the artisan communities are dispersed, often inaccessible, and almost invariably unorganized with low levels of literacy, education and living conditions. Because of their dispersed profile, they cannot band together and, as a consequence lack political weight and clout (Planning Commission, 2005). Yet, the declining production shows a decrease of artisans in every community. With modernization and industrialization, there is a gradual decline in handicrafts as they cannot compete with machine-made articles but this does not lead to a complete demise of handicrafts. The problem is that what had happened during the transitional period affects the mind of the

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younger generation leading to dependence on machine-made goods and unconsciously letting go of one's traditional and cultural heritage.

Most of the handicraft artisans belong to socially and economically weaker sections of the society in India (Muraleedharan, Anitha and Rugmini, 2009; Sundriyal & Sundriyal, 2009). According to the 2001 census, there were 15 million artisans in the country (Narasaiah & Naidu, 2006). The number of artisans in the country is difficult to obtain as they are much unorganized and mostly home-based workers (Das & Das, 2011). Indian Labour yearbook 2011 and 2012 reported that there is no authentic data on home base workers, it has been estimated that there are 48 lakh artisans and craft persons in India.

India has the largest area and the second-largest reserve of bamboo in the world. Forest resources and their usage is a major skill among many tribes (Thakur, 2009; Sahadevan, 2009). The North-Eastern region of India has the largest bamboo stock in the country which accounts for fifty-four per cent of the bamboo resources in India (Kakra & Bhattacharjee, 2009). A huge number of artisans in the North-Eastern part of India are still very much dependent on handicrafts. Mizoram, one of the North-Eastern regions of India has utilized bamboo in everyday life. Just like every other tribal state of India, Mizoram also produces many types of craft items but the number of artisans is not known. The interactional pattern and livelihood strategies have changed from the traditional ones, and social control mechanisms have also declined. Many tribes started migrating to other states in search of jobs and this has also accelerated their interaction with other castes and communities resulting in culture change (Sahadevan, 2009; Samal, 2006).

Several studies on artisans had been carried out by many researchers, however; these studies focus mainly on the traditional handicrafts such as pottery, blacksmithy, carpentry, silk weaving and basket weaving (Dutta & Ghose, 2010; Sahadevan, 2009; SEED, 2006; Narasaiah & Naidu, 2006; Scrase, 2005; Das & Sachdeva, 1993; Qureshi, 1990) which increased after the year 2000. An important section of artisans the bamboo and cane artisans have not gained adequate attention in most of these studies.

Therefore, a study on livelihood and living conditions of tribal artisans in Mizoram was carried out so that it might help the development of tribal artisans. It identifies their needs and problems so that these artisan communities can help themselves in achieving their full potential.

An Overview of Literature

Rural and tribal artisans constitute a notable proportion of India's population, the literature on their crafts, and their living condition is scarce. Among them, some studies had been focused on social aspects of tribal arts and crafts. Anthropologists and sociologists have attempted studies on tribal life, their culture, their relation with forest and their artistic skill with which they have decorated their simple life (Thakur, 2009; Sahadevan, 2009; Narasaiah & Naidu, 2006).

There are some studies which focus on commercial and economic aspects of tribal handicrafts (Narasaiah & Naidu, 2006). Tribal people have almost forgotten the technology and skill of their traditional occupations, and now these groups are engaged as wage labourers under local landlords and estates (Sahadevan, 2009).

Significantly, with the emergence of a globalised economy, coupled with postmodern consumer sentiments, crafts represent a traditional (or homely) form of consumer goods, which, for some buyers, gives them great appeal. In other words, the consumption of crafts allows for a symbolic (imagined) reconnection back to earlier, (traditional) and more "earthly" forms and designs in a fragmented, fractured and technological world (Scrase, 2005; Timothy, 2003).

The above overview of the literature suggests a few gaps. Firstly, there has not been any substantial study on artisans in North East India and the context of Mizoram tribal artisans; the relationship between livelihood and living has yet to be explored. Secondly, studies on tribal and rural artisans lack theoretical and empirical rigour. This present study addresses these research gaps with an application of Sustainable Livelihood Approach and probes into livelihood and living condition of artisans

Theoretical Framework: Sustainable Livelihood Framework

The Sustainable Livelihood approach is a tool for planning interventions, reviewing and evaluating projects, research, policy analysis and development. As Ellis(2000) wrote, the livelihoods approach is based on the premise that the asset status of the poor is fundamental to understanding the options open to them, the strategies they adopt to attain livelihoods, the outcomes they aspire to and the vulnerability context under which they operate. Department For International Development (DFID) distinguishes five categories of assets (or capital) – natural, social, human, physical and financial.

Robert Chambers and Gordon Conway (1992) in Krantz(2001) defined Livelihood as a livelihood comprising the capabilities, assets (stores, resources, claims and access) and activities required for a means of living. A livelihood is sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stress and shocks, maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets, and provide sustainable livelihood opportunities for the next generation; and which contributes net benefits to other livelihoods at the local and global levels and in the short and long term.

Statement of the Problem

The Mizos have many traditional handicraft products made from cane and bamboo. This skill had been passed on from one generation to the other until the machine-made products replaced them. However, there still are a few traditional handicraft items which machine-made items cannot replace and are highly socially valued. Unfortunately, there are only a few artisans left in Mizoram especially in Aizawl, who are engaged in such callings. Most of these artisans are recognized as the protectors of traditional handicrafts as they are the only means of preventing these handicrafts from extinction in the present industrialized world. Despite their importance and their value in the life of Mizo, artisans are decreasing and many of the traditional handicraft items might have gone forever along with the artisans. There are only a few central and state government programmes for the promotion of rural handicrafts and the living conditions of rural artisans. In this context, the study probes into the differential patterns of livelihood assets and living conditions of tribal bamboo and cane artisans in Mizoram between the rural and urban areas. Further, it explores the relationship between the livelihood assets and living conditions of them. In light of the findings, the study proposes a few suggestions for policy making and social work practice towards livelihood promotion of tribal artisans in the state.

Methodology

The current study has been conducted in two districts of Mizoram. Aizawl and Kolasib Districts. It is cross-sectional in nature and descriptive in design, and based on primary data collected mainly through field survey. The unit of the study is artisan household while the population of the study includes all the Cane and Bamboo handicraft artisan households in the districts of Aizawl and Kolasib.

The sampling procedure used was purposive. The sample size is 74 artisan households in which 58 artisan households are from the Rural Area and 16 are from the Urban Area. A pretested structured household interview

schedule was used for the collection of primary data. The interview schedule included sections on the demographic, social and economic profile, livelihood and living conditions of the artisans. The quantitative data collected through field survey was processed and analyzed with the help of MS Excel and SPSS and presented in the form of simple averages, percentages, cross-tabulation, and co-relation tables (Karl Pearson's Product Moment correlation coefficients).

Limitations of the Study

The target population is sparsely scattered all over the State considering the importance of the handicraft item. But those who sell and generate income from handicrafts are hard to find which create difficulties for the study. There can be no selection based on geographical area for the study as there is no record of the artisan population in Mizoram. There is a high possibility of unreached and left out artisans in the study as handicrafts consist of home-based work, and artisans are not visible for identification. Most of the respondents are identified through the market. The rural respondents are identified during their product sale in Aizawl and by directly visiting their village, while urban artisans are identified from their work in the Government sector, through their product sale in the market. Data collection was limited as communication is difficult due to language barrier in some areas where the interviewer has a chance of not obtaining the exact information s/he had in mind because of the need for interpretation by a translator. Time consumption rate is high in collecting data due to the artisan usually being engaged in agricultural or other work.

Results and Discussion

The results of the present study are presented in three sections. The first section is devoted to discussing the pattern of livelihood assets (natural capital, physical capital, financial capital, human capital and social capital). The pattern of living Conditions of the artisans is discussed in the second section while the relationship between the Livelihood and Living Conditions of the Tribal artisans is discussed in the last section.

Patterns of Natural Capital and Physical Capital

According to DFID (2000), natural capital is the natural resource stocks from which resource flows and services viz. land, water, forest, biodiversity degree, etc. useful for livelihoods are derived. The physical capital comprises the basic infrastructure and producer goods needed to support livelihoods, such as affordable transport, secure shelter and buildings, adequate water supply and sanitation, clean, affordable energy and access to information. In

the present paper, the size of landholding and the value of livestock owned by the household was considered as two indicators of the natural capital endowment. In the present study physical capital is assessed in terms of house, television, radio, utensils, furniture, solar plate, vehicle, cell phone and Jewelry. The total value of these assets was considered as the physical capital (see Table 1).

In terms both the natural and physical assets endowments, the urban artisans are better than those in the rural areas. There is not much difference in land ownership between rural and urban artisans. The analysed mean area owned by the artisan households shows that the access to land is slightly higher for the rural artisans (1.5 Acres) as compared to the urban artisans (1.3 Acres).

Table1 Pattern of Natural and Physical Assets

Sl. No.	Livelihood Asset	Location				Total N = 74	
		Urban n = 16		Rural n = 58			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
I	Natural Capital						
	Size of Land (In Acres)	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.3
	Live Stock (In Rs)	25063	79495	10778	13718	13866	38477
II	Physical Capital (In Rs)	169241	174239	5001	2925	40512	104302

Source: Computed

However, the monetary value of livestock owned by the urban artisan households was significantly greater than those owned by the rural artisans. The mean value of livestock owned by the urban artisan households was worked out to Rs. 25,063/- while the value of the rural household is Rs. 10,778/-. The physical assets owned by the urban artisan household were also significantly higher than those of the rural artisans. The urban artisan households own an average Rs. 16924/- worth of physical assets, that is three times higher than those of the rural artisans (Rs. 5001/-).

Table 2 Patterns of Financial Capital: Household Savings

(In Rs)

Form of Saving	Location				Total N = 74	
	Urban n = 16		Rural n = 58			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Cash in Hand	22750 (29.4)	15674	4560 (92)	3745	8493 (41.3)	10875
Commercial Banks	54500 (70)	55124	397 (8)	2649	12095 (58.7)	33656
Household Saving	77250(100)	63429	4957 (100)	4452	20588 (100)	41713

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Patterns of Financial Capital

In the present study, financial capital is assessed in terms of total household saving (see Table 2) and household debt (see Table 3). Household saving includes cash in hand and commercial bank savings/deposits while household debt includes money borrowed from friends and relatives, commercial banks, brokers, missionaries and grocery shop owners.

Concerning household saving, there is a significant difference between rural and urban artisan households. For the urban artisans, 71% of the savings was with the commercial banks while 92% of the savings of the rural artisans were in the form of cash in hand. Further, the total mean value of household savings of the urban artisans (Rs. 77,250/-) was far greater than Rs. 4,957/- savings of the rural artisans. The savings in the form of cash in hand, as well as deposits in commercial banks, were far greater for the urban artisan households as compared to the rural artisans (see Table 2).

Table 3 Patterns of Financial Capital: Household Debt

(In Rs)

Sl. No.	Form of Debt	Location				Total N = 74	
		Urban n = 16		Rural n = 58			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
	Friends and Relatives	0 (0.0)	0	34 (9.8)	184	27 (0.8)	163
	Commercial Banks	13438 (100)	23001	0 (0.0)	0	2905 (91.3)	11821
	Broker	0 (0.0)	0	224 (63.4)	586	176 (5.5)	526
	Missionaries	0 (0.0)	0	52 (14.6)	292	41 (1.3)	259
	Grocery shop	0 (0.0)	0	43 (12.2)	146	34 (1.1)	131
	Household Debt	13438 (100)	23001	353 (100)	683	3182 (100)	11768
	Financial Capital (Saving – Debt)	63813	68955	4603	4542	17405	39942

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages

As regards household debt too, there is a significant difference between rural and urban artisan households (see table 3). Artisan households in the urban are indebted mostly which is not so in rural areas, 63% of their debts in rural areas were with the brokers who help them sell their products. Household debt as a whole was greater for the urban artisans as compared to the rural artisans. The artisan households in the urban area had thirteen times (Rs. 13,438/-) higher amount of household debt as compared to those in the rural artisans (Rs. 353/-).

The net savings of the artisan households were considered as the financial capital endowment. There is a wide gap in the financial capital endowment between urban and rural artisan households. The mean value of the financial capital of the urban artisans was worked out to Rs. 63813/- while it was just Rs. 4603/- for the rural artisan households.

Patterns of Social Capital

Social Capital refers to the social resources upon which people draw in seeking for their livelihood outcomes, such as networks and contentedness, that increase people's trust and ability to cooperate or membership in more formalized groups and their systems of rules, norms and sanctions (DFID, 2000). In the present study, Social Capital was assessed in terms of three sets of indicators viz., Political participation (voting in elections), and Community participation (see Table 4).

Table 4 Patterns of Social Capital

Sl. No.	Indicators	Location				Total N = 74	
		Urban n = 16		Rural n = 58		Mean	S.D
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
I	Voting in Elections						
	General Election	3.0	0.0	2.8	0.8	2.8	0.7
	Assembly Election	3.0	0.0	2.9	0.6	2.9	0.5
	Village/Locality Council Election	3.0	0.0	2.9	0.6	2.9	0.5
	<i>Voting</i>	3.0	0.0	2.9	0.6	2.9	0.5
II	Community Participation						
	Village Council/Local Council	2.1	0.6	2.6	0.6	2.5	0.6
	Church-Based Organisations	1.7	0.6	2.0	1.2	1.9	1.1
	Young Mizo Association	2.1	0.9	0.0	0.0	0.5	1.0
	Mizo Hmeichhe Insuihkhawm Pawl	0.8	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.4
	Mizoram Upa Pawl	0.7	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.5
	<i>Community Participation</i>	1.5	0.3	0.9	0.3	1.0	0.4

Source: Computed

The first component of social capital is political participation assessed in terms of the frequency of voting in elections or electoral participation.

Voting in Elections included General election, Assembly Election and Village/Local Council Election. There is no significant difference in the patterns of political participation between rural and urban artisans. The Artisan households across the rural and urban areas have voted in all the general election, Assembly Elections and Local Council Elections.

There is no significant difference between the rural and urban artisans not only in modes of participation but also in the magnitude of political participation. In both locations, all of the respondent households had 'mostly' participated. There is no notable difference between the rural and urban artisan households in the pattern of political participation assessed in terms of voting in elections.

The second component of social capital is that of Community participation. It was assessed in terms of the frequency of the households' participation in Village Council/Local council, Church-Based Organisation, YMA, MHIP and MUP. The pattern of community participation of the urban artisan household was observed to be significantly different from those in rural areas. The artisans in the urban areas could participate in volunteering activities of all the community organisations such as Village Council/Local Council, Church-Based Organisations, Young Mizo Association, Mizo Hmeichhe Insuihkhawm Pawl (Mizo Women Association), Mizoram Upa Pawl (Association of Mizo Senior Citizens). The rural artisans could participate in only two modes of community volunteering through the Village Council/Local Council, and Church-Based Organisations. Hence, the community participation of artisan households is better in the urban area than in the rural area.

Patterns of Human Capital

In the context of a sustainable livelihood framework, human capital represents the skills, knowledge, ability to labour and good health that together enable people to pursue different livelihood strategies and achieve their livelihood objectives (DFID, 2000). In the present study, the human capital endowment of the artisan households has been assessed in terms of three discrete indicators- mean years of adult education, the proportion of earners and the number of artisans (see table 5).

Table 5 Patterns of Human Capital

Sl. No	Indicator	Location				Total N = 74	
		Urban n = 16		Rural n = 58			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	Mean Years of Adult Education	5.6	2.2	1.7	2.0	2.6	2.6
2	Proportion of Earners	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2
3	Number of Artisans	1.5	0.7	1.1	0.3	1.2	0.5

Source: Computed

The results of the analyses of the mean difference between the three indicators of human capital show that the artisans located in the urban areas have better endowment as compared those in the rural areas. The mean years of education of the adult members of the urban artisans (5.6) are significantly greater than that of the rural artisans (1.7). The proportion of earners in urban households (0.6) is also greater than that of the rural artisan households (0.3). Likewise, the number of artisans in urban artisan households (1.5) is also greater than that of the rural artisan households (1.1).

Patterns of Living Conditions of Artisans

Two indicators of the living conditions were used to assess the livelihood outcomes of the tribal artisans. They are household income and household expenditure. The pattern of household income of the artisan households was analysed in terms of its distribution across their sources. The common sources of Income for artisan households are Arts and crafts, Wage labour, Cultivation and others (see Table 6).